

Quantum Spin as an Operator on a Physical State which Replaces Vector Operations?

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The photon spin matrix ϵ_{ijk} (Levi-Civita symbol with i representing the matrix identifier and jk , its elements) follows from the continuity equation: $\frac{d}{dt} (\text{partial}) \{aE \cdot E + bB \cdot B\} + \text{grad} \cdot c E \times B$ (where E and B are electric and magnetic field vectors). The strategy (as shown in (1)), seems to be to replace the vector operator \times (cross product) with a matrix operator which acts on $(E+iB)$ (vector). This matrix also has eigenvectors and so represents an operator. Thus $-i\frac{d}{dx}$ partial and $i\frac{d}{dt}$ are operators which act on a probability distribution $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which has physical implications and spin seems to be associated with an operator which also may act on a physical state. In other words, a physical state or degree of freedom gives rise to vector operator properties and does not simply pull out a number like $i\frac{d}{dt}$ partial yielding E for a free particle.

We try to apply this idea to the Klein-Gordon equation $-\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} W(r,t) + \text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} W(r,t) = -m^2 W(r,t)$ ($c=1$). We argue that one wishes to replace the vector operation: dot product between grad and grad with an operator (matrix) which acts on a physical state (spinor). In other words, we argue that the vector operation of the dot product (like the cross product) in the photon case, is caused by an operator (which acts on a physical state). We note that one has quadratic type equations, so the one linearizes, with the operator, i.e. matrix, appearing in each expression. Thus one obtains anti-commutation relationships when creating the quadratic form by multiplying the two linear expressions without using any vector operations.

In other words, it is the presence of a physical state or degrees of freedom which automatically create the constraints introduced by the vector operator.

Photon Spin

One may write a continuity equation for a photon (from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations).

$$\frac{d}{dt} (\text{partial}) \{aE \cdot E + b B \cdot B\} + c \text{grad} \cdot E \times B = 0 \quad ((1))$$

Here E and B are electric and magnetic field 3-vectors and a, b, c constants. In principle, one may simply use ((1)) and not worry about spin. In (1), we showed one may factor out $E+iB$ from ((1)) to create a linear equation in $E+iB$. As a result, spin considerations seem to be thought of in terms of linearizing an equation, but also removing a vector operation. In such a case, one obtains the wave equation for a photon (see (1)):

$$\frac{d}{dt} (\text{partial}) \{E+iB\}_i + \epsilon_{ijk} \frac{d}{dx_j} (\text{partial}) \{E+iB\}_k = 0 \quad ((2))$$

Here ϵ_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol with i identifying the matrix and jk representing matrix elements. We argue that a key feature of ((2)) is that it removes the vector operator: cross product and replaces it with a matrix ϵ_{ijk} which carries the same information. The operator \times (cross product) indicates that E and B are perpendicular, but the Levi Civita symbol, acting as a matrix, does the same thing. In fact:

$$(\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B})_i = \epsilon_{ijk} E_j B_k \quad ((3))$$

The key feature is that ϵ_{ijk} acts as a matrix operator on a physical vector state. In other words, there is a physical degree of freedom associated with physical angular motion which creates the behaviour of the vector cross product. (One may note that the operator $-i\partial/\partial x$ acts on $\exp(ipx)$ in order to obtain the value p , but $\exp(ipx)$ represents physical fluctuations which manifest themselves in n-slit interference-diffraction experiments etc.) Here we suggest that physical motion (i.e. some kind of angular motion) is responsible for a vector operator (i.e. \times the cross product) and not a number i.e. p (momentum value).

We try to extend this idea to the Klein-Gordon equation.

Klein-Gordon Equation and Spin $\frac{1}{2}$

The Klein-Gordon equation follows from the special relativistic Lorentz invariant (dot product with a (1,-1) metric) :

$$-E^2 + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = m^2 c^2 \quad ((4)) \text{ with } E \rightarrow i\partial/\partial t \text{ and } \mathbf{p} \rightarrow -i \text{ grad } (\hbar=1) \quad ((5))$$

We note that $i\partial/\partial t$ and $-i \text{ grad}$ are operators which act on $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ to obtain E and a \mathbf{p} vector. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, however, has physical relevance because it is associated with an unusual probability in space and time which experimentally manifests itself in n-slit diffraction-interference experiments and in other situations (photon reflection-refraction). In other words, the component values of \mathbf{p} follow from the operator $-i \text{ grad}$ acting on a probability representing physical reality. We suggest that the dot product in $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$ in ((4)) should also result from an operator acting on a physical state. Given that one linearizes the quadratic form ((4)), but tries to write in terms of numbers or generalizations of numbers, i.e. matrices, it is the product of the two "number" like expressions which must replace the effect of the dot product.

In other words, physical degrees of motion should account for this dot product operation. How does one find this operator? As in the photon case, one may try to linearize the Klein-Gordon equation as Dirac already did. The point we wish to make is that by linearizing ((4)), one tries to write it as a product of two "numbers" i.e. removes the vector dot product which acts on vectors and not numbers. As a result, p_x, p_y and p_z all appear in the linearized "number" instead of appearing in a 3-vector.

As Dirac showed, one cannot use whole numbers to accomplish this, but may replace the vector dot product by introducing matrices which act as a generalized kind of number, but also operate on a vector which may be interpreted as a physical state or physical degree of freedom. Our objective is to replace a mathematical vector operator (dot product instead of cross product in the photon case) with a generalized number operator (matrix) which acts on a physical state. (Actually it is the product of these matrices which replace the dot product.)

It is then the physical state which is ultimately linked to the operator which creates the same effect as the mathematical vector operator, i.e. the dot product in this case.

In other words, one wishes to have matrices such that:

$S_x p_x + S_y p_y + S_z p_z$ yields a matrix B so: that

$$S_x S_y + S_y S_x = 0, S_x S_z + S_z S_x = 0, S_y S_z + S_z S_y = 0$$

and $S_x S_x = S_y S_y = S_z S_z = I$ (identity matrix) ((6))

Even though the dot product applies to 3-vectors, a set of 2x2 matrices may satisfy condition ((6)). In the photon case, a 3x3 matrix is needed. These S_x, S_y, S_z matrices are the Pauli matrices. They act on a two vector i.e. the basis (1,0) (0,1) for S_z . This suggests there exists physically two degrees of freedom in the system for each coordinate x,y,z. If one is in a state (1,0) (eigenvector for S_z), one does not know the state for S_x or S_y . (1,0) is called a spin up state (for the z axis) and (0,1) a spin down. These states are physical. Experimentally, they are found to be linked to angular momentum and interact with a magnetic field. A spin up state may interact with a magnetic field along the z axis in a different way than a spin down.

The main point we wish to make is that these physical states, represented by vectors, are linked with specific operators (matrices) which, when multiplied together through the multiplication of two linear number-like (matrix) expressions, replace a vector operation (the dot product for the Klein-Gordon equation). In other words, the effect of the dot product is created by physical states. We argue that this is the significance of spin. The spin states are linked with Pauli matrices which only allow $p_x p_x$ $S_x S_x$ or $p_y p_y$ $S_y S_y$ or $p_z p_z$ $S_z S_z$ to remain, but allow no cross terms e.g. $S_x S_y + S_y S_x$, $S_x S_z + S_z S_x$ or $S_y S_z + S_z S_y$. In other words, physical states (degrees of freedom) ensure this result.

We further note that $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ is a scalar probability distribution and that in statistics, one multiplies probabilities by a number to create an average. Here the number arises from the action of an operator $-i \text{grad}$, but we argue that the $p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$ feature may arise from other operators (Pauli matrices) linked with different physical degrees of freedom. Thus not only are the values p_x, p_y, p_z associated with a physical probability $\exp(i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, but the vector dot product as well, namely a spinor.

The above discussion, however, applies to the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ case for the Klein-Gordon equation. This equation may also have a spin 0 solution and still contain $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$. Thus, spin $\frac{1}{2}$ is a special case. We also note that Dirac created 4x4 matrices which contain the 2x2 Pauli matrices. His solution allows for positive and negative energies (i.e. particles and antiparticles).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that spin seems to arise from the wish to find an operator (matrix in this case) which acts on a physical state (spinor for spin .5, vector for spin 1) and reproduces (when two linear matrix type expressions are multiplied together) the effect of a vector operator which exists in a quadratic type equation. In the case of a photon, the quadratic type equation is the continuity equation which may be linearized (see (1)) so that the vector cross product is replaced by \mathbf{e}_{ijk} (Levi-Civita symbol with i identifying the matrix and jk its elements) acting on $\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B}$ (where \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are the electric and magnetic field vectors). \mathbf{e}_{ijk} then acts on a vector representing a physical state. In other words, a physical state, associated with a spin matrix

reproduces the effects of a vector operation, namely the cross product. (when one multiplies to $(E + iB)$ with a linear photon wave equation with wavefunction $E + iB$ i.e. ((2))

In the case of the Klein-Gordon equation, the vector operator is the dot product: $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$, where \mathbf{p} is the momentum vector. The operator $-i \text{grad}$ acting on $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p}\cdot\mathbf{x})$ is sufficient to obtain the value of p_x , p_y and p_z , but the dot product behaviour must be obtained from another operator one which acts like a generalized number i.e. matrix which ensures no mixing of terms like $p_x p_y$, $p_y p_z$ or $p_x p_z$. One wishes to write the quadratic expression containing the vector operator (dot product) as two linear generalized number-type expressions containing matrices. This yields constraints on matrix products, i.e. $S_x S_y + S_y S_x = 0$, $S_x S_z + S_z S_x = 0$ and $S_y S_z + S_z S_y = 0$ and $S_x S_x = S_y S_y = S_z S_z = 1$.

A set of 2x2 matrices may satisfy this condition. These are the well-known Pauli matrices and they operate on two- vectors (spinors). There are two degrees of freedom i.e. physical states associated with each dimension. These physical states, in turn, are associated with matrix operators which may reproduce the action of vector operators, in particular the cross product in the photon case and the dot product in the Klein-Gordon spin .5. case. The physical states in question seem to be associated with angular type motion as noted experimentally .Both the dot and cross product may also be linked with rotational type features. For example, the dot product is invariant under a rotation of the coordinate system and the cross product ensures the linking of a component of one vector with a component rotated 90 degrees in the second vector, so to speak.

References

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